

TECHNISCHE
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Detection of Toxicity in Online Comments

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Lead partner:	TU-Wien
Version:	1.0
Status:	Closed
Dissemination level:	PU: Public
Document link:	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11068659

Detection of Toxicity in Online Comments has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. .

Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Detection of Toxicity in Online Comments project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

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DELIVERY SLIP

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DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
1.0	19.04.2024		Roland Ramp

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Roland Ramp will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	ToxicBERT	Other	safetensors	1 GB	no
P2	NERToxicBERT	Other	safetensors	1 GB	no

The trained transformer classification and the named entity recognition model are stored in a domain specific format (see transformers on huggingface.io). [DOI 10.57967/hf/2085](https://doi.org/10.57967/hf/2085) and [DOI 10.57967/hf/2094](https://doi.org/10.57967/hf/2094) The format is a domain specific one (safetensors plus JSON and TXT). The file size is smaller than 1 GB.

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	German BERT base	https://huggingface.co/deepset/gbert-base	MIT	no

R2	nlp2023_toxic_german	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11039040	closed	no
R3	nkekat1000/toxic-bert-german	https://huggingface.co/ankekat1000/toxic-bert-german	CC-BY-NC-SA	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The model created during the experiments is produced using the closed data set of toxicity data [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11039040](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11039040). To do this experiments software located in a GitHub repository is used [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11068370](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11068370). Also detailed description on how to do experiments is included in the source codes README.md files. The research data reused is structured and of JSON type with a file size of about 2 Mb. And as the dataset is closed only the metadata is provided. A detailed description on the file structure is located in the sourcecode data directory. The pretrained Models reused are of the safetensors type and accompanied by additional files of JSON ant TXT format and about 500Mb each.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community working on language specific tasks in the field of natural language processing (NLP).

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The research data (nlp2023_toxic_german) will be provided via a private GitHub repository. The data is structured with a JSON datatype and the file size is about 2 Mb. There is no versioning of this dataset as it is only used readonly. After data preparation (lemmatization, POS,) the data set is saved in a structured files with the CoNLLU file

format. Size will be also rather small (<100Mb). As this data is only an intermediary result and falls also under the closed data agreement, this dataset will not be shared.

As the nlp2023_toxic_german is closed only the metadata following the Dublin Core standard are published under [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11039040](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11039040) also including the contact person and actual data location.

The metadata of the models (German BERT base and nkekat1000/toxic-bert-german) used for finetuning are located in the model cards on huggingface. The format is machine learning domain specific format.

The NLP (Natural Language Processing) Models are provided via huggingface.io. The file format is a domain specific (transformer safetensors, JSON) and the file size is about 500 Mb per model. Models produced during the training will be versioned on the filesystem (timestamp_modelname_random_number)

We will be using the following domain specific metadata standards: For the non public dataset metadata will be provided following the standard Dublin Core.

For the NLP-Models there are modelcards on huggingfaces. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1(ToxicBERT)	Open		2023-11-25	Hugging Face Hub	DOI 10.57967/hf/2085	MIT
P2(NERToxicBERT)	Open		2023-11-25	Hugging Face Hub	DOI 10.57967/hf/2094	MIT

Repository description:

Different repositories are used during this project.

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and Pj Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com>

Hugging Face Hub is a platform (centralized web service) for hosting, Git-based code repositories, including discussions and pull requests for projects. Models, also with Git-based version control, Datasets, mainly in text, images, and audio. Web applications ("spaces" and "widgets"), intended for small-scale demos of machine learning applications.

Methods or software needed to access and use data:

The source code of the software needed to train a model on toxicity is located on GitHub and can be accessed through the following [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11094355](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094355), which Zenodo utilizes to provide access to all versions the source code. All the needed requirements are described in a readme in the code repository. The source code is publicly available.

The created models are located on the Hugging Face Hub under the following [DOI 10.57967/hf/2085](https://doi.org/10.57967/hf/2085) and [DOI 10.57967/hf/2094](https://doi.org/10.57967/hf/2094). They contain a domain (ML) specific model card containing metadata and description. The models itself are publicly available under the MIT license.

The access protocol is standardized for the domain (Git or via Huggingface API) and free. No user identification is needed.

All the metadata provided is available under the CC-0 license (Creative Commons).

Metadate is provided via Huggingface and GitHub and will be available as long as these services are in operation. There is no plan of deleting the data in the future.

Documentation will be included in the model card (metadata) with a detailed instruction how to use the model.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. Here the provided Models are described in model cards (domain specific metadata and description). As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our model. There is also a link to the source code producing this model linked as well as the reference of the meta data of the data used training this model. This source code also contains detailed description in readme files.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata (model card) and the models itself.

The model card contains a detail description on how the model was produced and how it can be reused and further finetuned. Further the source code is linked with detailed description on how training a model and doing data preparation.

The experiments source code will be provided on GitHub [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11094355](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094355). Source code contains a detailed README.md file describing how the experiment can be reproduced. (If access to needed data is possible) All required libraries are listed in a requirements.txt file and installation instructions are also included in the README.md. Needed file system structure also comes with the project source code. Including description were to put the data and where the results will be stored.

In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The model obtained is published Open Access under a MIT license, provided there are no data protection concerns concerning this model.

The following data quality checks were done: hyperparameter tuning and model evaluation.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to

provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

As research output there was also a presentation and a management summary produced, which is published under the following [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11094289](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094289).

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR as outlined below.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Model backup storage	File-based Storage	For backups of the experiments a cloud provider will be used. The backups will be stored encrypted.	EUR	1.000
GPU	Hardware and Infrastructure	For GPU accelerated experiments a GPU capable computer be used.	EUR	2.000
Personal	Personal	Data manager	EUR	5.000
Legal Advice	Legal Advice	On publishing models a lawyer will be consulted	EUR	1.000
Estimated total costs				9.000

Coverage of costs:

...

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with Roland Ramp being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

P1 (ToxicBERT) and P2 (NER ToxicBERT) will be stored for backup reasons on TUfiles after each experiment: TUfiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by TU.it. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

The trained models are stored on Huggingface Hub (linked with GitHub). Backups and security will be provided via the Huggingface platform.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

Only the dataset R2 is considered as sensitive data in the project.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	writing
P2	writing	writing	writing
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	No access	No access
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	Hugging Face Hub	10 years
P2	Hugging Face Hub	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

There was no processing of any personal data in the project.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

Legal restrictions on how data is processed and shared are specified in the confidentiality agreement. The restrictions relate to datasets R2 (nlp2023_toxic_german). The legal restrictions are based on the following: Mutual Confidentiality Agreement

Pia Pachinger Data Science Group TU-Wien has rights to the produced data and controls access.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?